

Numerical Modelling of Local Scour Around Cylindrical Piers Including Secondary Flows Effects

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Abstract—The aim of the present study is to provide a computational low-cost numerical model be able calculating the local scour around bridge piers at a temporal and spatial scale of the river. A mathematical model based on the shallow waters equations including a parameterization of effects of secondary flows is presented. This mathematical model was implemented in Open Telemac software by modifying its source code in order to build the numerical model. In order to perform the parameterization of effects of secondary flows present in the phenomenon, a three-dimensional modeling of the flow field and local scour was performed using sedFoam computational tool implemented in OpenFoam. To carry out the calibration and / or validation of the proposed model, a measurement campaign was carried out in the Roncador Bridge piers located on the Magdalena River at the height of the town of Magangue, Bolivar. The measurements consisted in obtaining velocity data, depth of the water sheet, bathymetries and grain size of the bed. Measurements of velocity and depth of the water sheet were obtained with an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). The bathymetries were performed with an echo sounder and a sonar type deeper. The bed shear stresses that are generated around the pile along with the scour holes in equilibrium and the velocity fields modified by the proposed model are presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

Local scour in cylindrical piers is a highly complex phenomenon due to its three-dimensional behavior with highly turbulent processes acting in a bed that variable in time and space. The field of flow around a cylindrical pier is composed mainly of two vortex systems, the horseshoe-vortex and the wake-vortex, this vortex being generated at the moment in which the fluid comes into contact with the contour of the pier, of this very close to the contour, the velocity of the main flow should decrease drastically, which would produce a pressure gradient in the opposite direction to the flow (adverse pressure gradient), the boundary-layer adhered to the surface of the pier cannot withstand this adverse pressure gradient what produces an inversion of the flow and likewise a separation of the boundary-layer, this separation causes a rotational flow behind the pile, the so-called wake vortices.

The so-called horseshoe-vortex are produced by the approach flow to the pier, just at the moment when the flow hits upstream against the pile generates a gradient of pressures. Some researchers associate the formation of this gradient of pressures to the pressure of stagnation, which is a function of the density of

the fluid multiplied by the square of the velocity divided by 2 (Raudkivi A., 1986) [12]. If the pressure gradient that forms at the front of the pier is strong enough it generates a vertical downward flow, which in turn generates a three-dimensional detachment of the boundary layer, the downward flow along with this detachment ends up colliding with the bottom forming the horseshoe-vortex, which are transported downstream of the pile (Dargahi, 1990) [4].

Both the wake-vortex that acts as a vacuum and the horseshoe-vortex that directly strike the bed are the main mechanism of local scour.

Some researchers have proposed empirical or semi-empirical equations to calculate the maximum depth of scour as a function of average flow velocity, grain diameter, and depth of flow and diameter of the pile. These investigations are divided into two when there is a transport of bed sediments (Live-Bed) Neil, 1964 [10], Breusers HN, 1977 [2], Roulund et al, 2005 [15] and when there is no transport of bed sediments (Clear water) Laursen, 1960 [7], Jain & Fisher, 1979 [6], Raudkivi & Ettema, 1986 [13] and Vittal, 1994 [16]. These contributions have given glimpses of the behavior of the maximum depth that can occur in the pile, this behavior as a function of the approach velocity is shown in Fig 1.

Figure 1. Maximum depth of scour as a function of the average flow velocity [8]

Fig. 1 shows two types of curves with similar behavior, the upper curve represents the average depth of scouring for coarse sediments ($d_{50} \geq 0.8$ mm) and the lower curve the depth of scouring for fine sediments ($d_{50} < 0.8$ mm), it is important to note

that for coarse sediments the maximum scour depth occurs just when the approach velocity is equal to the critical velocity, whereas for fine sediments the maximum scour occurs when the approach velocity is four times the critical velocity. It is also observed that for coarse sediments the scour is greater ($2.5 * D$) than for fine sediments ($2.0 * D$).

Due to the advance in computing that has been generated in recent years the phenomenon has been addressed using numerical or computational modeling, one of the first contributions to the subject was made by Olsen & Melaaen (1993) [11] who used the Navier-Stokes equations with the Reynolds average approach, this was the first three-dimensional model that was proposed in the literature that calculated the hydro-morphodynamics of the scour around bridge piers in a non-cohesive bed under clear water conditions. Other investigations such as these are those made by Richardson & Pancheng (1998) [14], Roulund et al (2005) [15], and Nagata et al (2005) [9]. On the other hand, Escarriaza & Sotiropoulos (2011) [5] were the first to model the undermining dynamics using the Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) and Detached-Eddy Simulation (DES) turbulence models to represent the flow around a circular bridge pier, in addition to coupling a Lagrangian bed transport model.

Finally, Chauchat et al (2017) [3] proposed a three-dimensional and two-phase solver for sediment transport applications, the mathematical model implemented is based on the volume of fluid (VOF) approach, therefore the sediment phase is modeled as a continuous, this tool allows to use several turbulence models ($k-\epsilon$, $k-\omega$ and Mixing Length) and two different models of intergranular stress (Kinetic theory of granular flows and dense granular flow Rheology).

This solver (SedFoam) was used in the present investigation to establish the three-dimensional flows that occur around the pier over time, that is, as the scour hole develops, this with the intention of being able to parameterize the secondary flows (Vertical flows) that occur around the phenomenon.

II. NUMERICAL MODEL

From the construction and analysis of three-dimensional numerical models, both hydrodynamic and morphodynamic, and from the detailed description of the phenomenon, a parameterization of the vertical flows (secondary flows) that occur around the bridge piers was determined.

The pisoFoam solver was used to determine the hydrodynamics of the phenomenon, pisoFoam is a transient solver for incompressible and turbulent flows that using the PISO algorithm, Fig. 2 shows the graphical results that show the velocity fields that are presented around a pile and that were calculated for fixed bed, in the figure the formation of the wake vortices is clearly seen (back side of the pile) and the horseshoe vortices (front face of the pile), in addition, the pressure gradient upstream of the pile was determined and calculated.

As previously mentioned, a modeling was performed with the SedFoam solver to determine the flow fields around the pile when a scour hole is generated, in Fig. 3 the shape of the scour hole generated for a 42 hours simulation is shown. With the analysis of these two models, the following mathematical model is presented based on the shallow water equations and

their results compared with data obtained in the Magdalena River.

Figure 2. Three-dimensional flow field around bridge pier (Flow is from left to right).

Figure 3. Three-dimensional and hydrosedimentological model of local scour around in bridge piers (Flow is from right).

A. Hydrodynamic Model

The governing equations for the flow are the depth-averaged shallow-water equations which are Saint Venant equations in two dimensions, this hydrodynamic model presents two momentum equations and an equation of continuity. These equations in Cartesian coordinates can be expressed as:

- Continuity Equation

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

- Momentum Equations

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -g \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + \frac{\rho}{h} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \right) + S_x \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = -g \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} + \frac{\rho}{h} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} \right) + S_y \quad (3)$$

Where x and y are the Cartesian coordinates, u and v are the components of the velocity in the x -direction and y -direction, respectively, h is the depth of the water, H is the elevation of the water surface, that is, the depth of the water more the elevation of the bed (Z_b) and S_x and S_y are source terms that in the present investigation refer to the friction produced in the bed, this is calculated from the shear stress in the bed τ_x and τ_y and these stresses can be expressed from of the Manning equation as:

$$S_x = -\frac{\tau_x}{h\rho} = -\frac{gn^2 u \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}}{h^{4/3}} \quad (4)$$

$$S_y = -\frac{\tau_y}{h\rho} = -\frac{gn^2 v \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}}{h^{4/3}} \quad (5)$$

Where ρ is the density of water, g is the acceleration due to gravity and n is the roughness coefficient of Manning.

B. Morphodynamic Model

The prediction of bathymetric changes and sediment discharges are calculated from a morphodynamic model which is coupled to the hydrodynamic model so that sediment transport and flow occur simultaneously, this model contains a transport component of non-cohesive bed sediments and a component of the bed evolution from the conservation of the mass of sediments that can be expressed in Cartesian coordinates such as:

$$(1-\lambda) \frac{\partial Z_b}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q_{bx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_{by}}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Where Q_{bx} and Q_{by} are the components of the solid transport vector ($\vec{Q}_b$) in the x and y directions respectively, Z_b is the bed elevation as previously mentioned and λ is the porosity of the bed. Q_{bx} and Q_{by} is calculated from the background sediment transport rate as:

$$Q_{bx} = Q_b \cos \alpha \quad Q_{by} = Q_b \sin \alpha \quad (7)$$

Where α is the angle between the solid transport vector and the downstream direction, i.e. with respect to the x coordinate axis, the bed sediment transport rate Q_b is calculated from empirical bed transport equations, in the present investigation the Meyer-Peter and Muller equations and the Einstein-Brown equation were used. These equations are defined according to the number of Shields that can be expressed as

$$\theta = \frac{\mu \tau_b}{(\rho_s - \rho) g d} \quad (8)$$

Where τ_b is the shear stress at the bottom, ρ_s is the density of the sediment that is normally assumed to be 2.65 kg/m³, d is the characteristic diameter of the sediment, which for uniform sediments is equal to d_{50} and μ is a factor of correction due to the background friction that is calculated from a relationship between coefficients of friction:

$$\mu = \frac{C'_f}{C_f} \quad C'_f = 2 \left(\frac{\kappa}{\log(12h/ks)} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

Where κ is the von Karman coefficient which is equal to 0.4, the roughness height ks is a function of the sediment diameter $ks = \xi_s d_{50}$ and the coefficient ξ_s is a parameter to be calibrated. Finally, the transport equations of bottom sediments that were used in the present investigation are presented:

- Meyer-Peter & Muller Equation

$$Q_b = \chi \sqrt{(g(s-1)d^3(\theta - \theta_{cr}))^{3/2}} \quad (10)$$

- Einstein-Brown Equation

$$Q_b = \sqrt{(g(s-1)d^3 \left(\frac{2}{3} + \frac{36}{d} \right)^{0.5} - \left(\frac{36}{d} \right)^{0.5}} * f(\theta) \quad (11)$$

$$f(\theta) = \begin{cases} 2.15 e^{-0.391/\theta} & \text{if } \theta \leq 0.2 \\ 40\theta^3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Where θ_{cr} is the number of critical Shields that is equal to 0.047 for particle diameters between 0.2 and 2 mm, χ is a coefficient or parameter for calibration and that by default is taken as equal to 8, s is the relative sediment density and is equal to $s = \rho_s / \rho$, it must be taken into account in the case of the Meyer-Peter & Muller equation if the number of Shields is less than the number of Shields critical the bottom sediment transport rate is equal to zero, On the other hand, the parameter d_d in the Einstein-Brown equation is equivalent to $d_d = d[(s-1)g/\vartheta^2]^{1/3}$, where ϑ is the viscosity of the water.

Finally, the shear stress in the bottom is calculated, which depends on the velocity and a term associated with the pressure and the secondary flows around the pile, this effort is expressed as follows:

$$\tau_b = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_f (u^2 + v^2) + L \quad [13]$$

III. DESCRIPTION OF FIELD DATA

In order to carry out a validation and / or calibration of the proposed model, a measurement campaign was carried out at different times of the year on the Magdalena River at the height of the town of Magangué, Bolivar, (See Figure 4). Over the river it extends the Roncador or Celeste bridge, which has a length of 2.3 km, a width of 15 m and a height of 32 m, in the bed of the river were built 4 piers with pile cap of 9 circular piles of 4 m in diameter, the campaign is composed of measurements of flow, bathymetries of the bed, granulometry and depth of sheet of water. The study section on the Magdalena River has a length of approximately 18 km, an average width of 600 m and an average depth of 15 m, to 7.6 km downstream of Magangué the river bifurcates generating an island (Isla Grande), the arm left to 1.2 km downstream again bifurcates generating a second island (See Fig. 4), finally the three arms are joined again at the height of Puerto Kennedy. Below are each of the equipment used in the measurements with their respective results.

Figure 4. Section of study on the Magdalena River.

A. Flow Data

The flow and velocity data were collected with an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) of Teledyne RD Instruments brand, River Ray model which contains 3 transducers that work with a frequency of 600 kHz, in total 5 flow measurements were taken, the first at the height of Magangué in which velocities were obtained between 1.9 m / s and 0.5 m / s, a maximum depth of 17.22 m and a total flow of 4636 m³ / s, in figure 5 the magnitude of the velocity at along the cross-section of the river, two more measurements were made just after the first fork where the left arm reported velocities between 1.6 m / s and 0.4 m / s, the maximum depth was 5.9 m and a total flow of 1465 m³ / s, the right arm presented velocities between 0.2 m / s and 1.9 m / s, the maximum depth

was 10 m and a total flow of 3359 m³ / s, then measurement was made just after the bridge piles on the right arm and were obtained velocities between 2.1 m / s and 0.6 m / s, a maximum depth of 14.2 m and a total flow of 3454 m³ / s, finally a last measurement was taken downstream of the bifurcation, which showed velocities between 0.7 m / s and 2.2 m / s, a maximum depth of 16.6 m and a total flow of 4836 m³ / s.

B. Bathymetry Data

The bathymetric data was collected with two echo sounders, the first of Valeport brand and MIDAS Surveyor GPS model, which contains 2 transducers one high frequency (210 kHz) and one low frequency (33 kHz), the working resolution is 0.01 m, the second Garmin echosounder model ECHOMAP Plus 64cv, which contains two working frequencies of 50 kHz and 200 kHz, the echo sounder has a resolution of 0.1m. Bathymetric data were obtained before construction of the bridge piers and two measurements were taken at different times of the year, in total approximately 20,000 points were obtained in the entire study section, these measurements yielded maximum depth data of 23 m. that generates levels below sea level, in figure 6 the bathymetric points raised before the construction of the bridge piers are observed, it can be seen that there is data between 12 m above sea level and -13 m above sea level, with this bathymetric information it was able to calculate the slope of the total river bed, that is, from end-to-end of the stretch and the maximum and minimum slopes between sections, which were 0.000522 m / m, 0.0302 m / m, 0.00147 m / m respectively.

The topography of the sector was obtained from the Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) technology with an airplane over flight having heights above sea level with resolutions of 5X5 m.

C. Granulometry Data

The granulometric data were taken with a steel drill reinforced with iron weights, which stabilize the sampling, 6 samples of bottom sediments were obtained, 3 in the right arm of the river and 3 in the other arm, in each arm was taken 2 relatively close to the edges and the last in the center of the cross-section. Then in the laboratory, specialized equipment Battersize was used to obtain the granulometric curve and have the mean diameter (d50) of the sediment.

D. Georeferenced Data

To make the georeferencing of the bathymetric points, the Hypack® Lite software was used, which allows bathymetric lifting with a coupling between a georeferencing instrument and an echo sounder, this results in points with planimetric information and also with elevation above sea level. In this measurement campaign, a Real Time Kinematic receiver (RTK) Sokkia brand model GRX2 was used as a georeferentation instrument.

Figure 5. Magnitude of velocity along the cross section of the Magdalena River with ADCP.

Figure 6. Bathymetric points before construction of bridge piers.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The numerical model was implemented on the OpenTelemac solvers suite whose code was modified according to the model proposed in the present investigation. In principle, the Telemac2D solver coupled with the Sysiphe morphodynamic model was used, using two bed transport equations that were presented in numeral 2, in the present investigation the transport of sediments in suspension was not considered because the study carried out by Baker (1986) suggests that the effect of sediments in suspension are not radically significant in terms of the depth of scour in equilibrium, in this way two simulations were carried out with variable boundary conditions in time (Unsteady), starting with the data collected before the construction of the bridge piers, these simulated 7 days that had a computational cost of 8 hours each, the results of these simulations are presented below.

A. Velocity

The velocity field in the x-direction and y-direction is shown in Figure 7, in this image it is appreciated the 9 piles of the second Roncador Bridge pier, in the image on the left it can see the velocity in a color palette where red represents velocities above 1.26 m/s and the blue velocities below 0.14 m/s, in this image and in the following images the direction of the flow is from bottom to top, in the walls of the piles a no-slip boundary condition was applied, this is why low velocities are presented around them, this was done to simulate the velocity profile at the contact of a wall and with this the detachment of the boundary layer, in front of the piles the

stagnation point is observed where the velocity drops abruptly by an increase in pressure, this leads to an elevation of the water surface in front of each pile.

In the image on the right of Fig. 7, the vector velocity field is presented, where high velocities (greater than 1.53 m/s) are represented by the red color and long vectors and low velocities (less than 0.17 m/s) are represented by the color blue and short vectors, in these two images it can see behind each pile an area where the velocity is low and it increases as it moves away from the pile, in the simulations carried out no wake vortices were generated, This is because the distance between piles is very short and the wake behind each pile does not have enough space to move and collides with the next pile, in the last row of piles the strength and velocity of the flow is reduced and not the vortices are produced, besides it is observed that the flow that does not hit the piles is not altered too much by the accelerations or decelerations that take place inside the matrix of 9 piles. This wake that is observed behind the last row of piles extends several tens of meters affecting the flow field downstream of the piles.

Figure 7. Velocity around the bridge group piers.

Figure 8. Velocity vector around the bridge group piers.

B. Bed Shear Stress

The bed shear stress is shown in Figure 8 which was calculated from equation 13 which is a function of the velocity, in this figure the bed shear stress is plotted from isolines, from this way the red isolines represent efforts greater than 8.1 N/m² and the blue isolines represent efforts less than 0.9 N/m², in the image it is appreciated that the shear stress follows a pattern similar to the velocity field, i.e., areas where at high velocities, high shear stress occur and vice-versa.

In figure 9 it is observed that the bed shear stress upstream of the pile is very low, almost zero, due to the low velocity that is generated in this area, on the lateral sides of the piles a fast change in the shear stress where it increases almost from zero to 7.2 N/m².

Figure 9. Bed shear stress around the bridge group piers.

C. Scour

The depth of scour around the piles is shown in Figure 9, which was calculated from a bed transport equation that is a function of the shear stress in the bed and the number of Shields, finally from the spacial and temporal discretization of the Exner equation gives a change in the depth of the bed in each element of the computational domain.

In the image it is observed that the depth of the bed around the piles is plotted from isolines such as the shear stress, in this way, the light green to red isolines represent areas of granular material deposition and the isolines between the dark blue and dark green are areas that represent areas of scouring.

In the Fig. 10, it is clearly seen that the biggest scour occurs on the sides of the individual piles at approximately 45° of the axis parallel to the flow, this scour is joined with the scour of the pile next to it causing a damping effect of the scour, furthermore, it can be seen that on the back face of the piles, sedimentation zones have generated that join with the front face of the immediately following pile.

Figure 10. Local Scour around the bridge group piers.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the present investigation we present a two-dimensional numerical model that parameterizes the effects of secondary flows such as the vertical flows that appear in the front and back face of a circular and vertical pile, this model was validated and/or calibrated with data taken in the field on the Magdalena river at the height of the municipality of Magangué, to perform the parameterization, three-dimensional numerical models were used, both hydrodynamic and sedimentological, which were useful to determine the magnitude of the vertical flows and their incidence in the process of local scour.

The hydrodynamic model is based on the saint-venant equations and is coupled with a morphodynamic model that uses the Exner equation to calculate changes in bed depth, the numerical results showed that the present model is capable of capturing all the characteristics. The main undermining of the local scouring process, including those generated by the vertical flows showed that the maximum undercut in all the simulations did not exceed 2.5 m and that the depth of undermining in equilibrium was simulated quite well, finding small differences of maximum 10%.

The parameterization of the vertical flows is made from a modification of the shear stress equation in the bed, where a term that is in function of the pressure is added and allows to simulate the scour produced by these vertical flows, especially in the part at the front of the piles, the results show that the addition of this parameter is capable of generating the scour considerably, taking into account that the spatial and temporal scales are difficult to represent.

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